

Student Radicalism in Hungary: A Survey of Corvinus University Students

Anirban Banerjee*

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to examine whether Hungarian students are in favour of radical social change. With this objective in mind, a pilot study was carried out in 14th November, 2011 at the Institute of Sociology and Social Policy, Corvinus University, among the MA students. All the students of two MA classes, who were present, participated in the survey. We find that out of 32 students, who participated, 17(53.17%) were not acquainted with Marxism, and, therefore, had no attitude to radical social change. Of the remaining fifteen students, 6 (40%) were conservatives and 9(60%) were liberals. There were no radicals among the students surveyed. Though it is a micro-study, it shows that educated Hungarian youth have strong views on the major social, economic and political issues facing nation. They are also conscious of their political rights and citizenship duties like voting. The author has made some policy prescriptions and suggested directions for future research.

Keywords: *Radicalism, Students, Collective Consciousness, Student Politics, Political Socialization*

Introduction

In all countries students are regarded as important agents of radical social change. Students are the most organized and enlightened section of the youth. "The student wing should herald the new, only then do they deserve to be called the promise of tomorrow. A better tomorrow", writes Poonam Jain in The Views paper (9). The present study, which is a pilot study on student radicalism in Hungary, was made as part of a visit to Hungary by the author on a scholarship from the Hungarian Scholarship Board. The author came to Hungary as part of the Indo-Hungarian Education Exchange Programme (2011). The study was conducted in the Institute of Sociology & Social Policy of Corvinus University, Budapest.

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Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the present study is to see whether the concept of student radicalism, developed in the sixties of the twentieth century, is applicable to twenty-first century Hungary. Hungary presents an interesting case of a society in transition. Till the late eighties, Hungary was a Communist state. But the great upheaval against Communism which began in 1989 and continued till the demise of the Soviet Union in the early nineties resulted in the demise of Communism in Eastern Europe including Hungary. How do the Hungarian students, who are the vanguard of the nation's youth, view their society today?

Student Power in Hungary

Hungarian students have played an important political role in Hungary since the revolution of 1848, led by Louis Kossuth (10) Contemporary Hungary is undergoing rapid changes and this has affected Hungarian social and political attitudes. Zsolt Enyedi and Bojan Tojosevecié(1) in their study of organization of political attitudes in Hungary found that Hungarian mass attitudes vary along conventional socialist conservatism, right wing conservatism and libertarianism. The latter three positions polarise Hungarian politics into three oppositions: old versus new regime, religious –nationalist right. Comparing Serbia with Hungary, Todosijević writes that in both countries authoritarianism proved to be an important determinant of ideological dimensions, especially of pro-communist nationalism in Serbia and right-wing conservatism in Hungary.(8) Recent events show that Hungary is moving to the right. For example, Hungary has equated Soviet era crimes with that of the Nazis. (19)

News reports indicate that the student community is also moving towards the right. Paul Hockenos (2) shows that college kids are favouring the right-wing political leader, Jobbik, and his Movement for a Better Hungary and are deeply hostile to the Roma gypsies. Jobbik is popular among poor, unemployed youth. Another news report (4.) virtually echoes Hockenos. A recent survey by sociologist, Luca Varádi, of 1000 teenagers in 23 Hungarian schools found that 72 per cent had at least one negative feeling about the Roma. Based on the answers, 32 percent would be considered extremely racist. The majority of the students identified Roma as foreigners (5.)

Recently, the education policy of the Government of Hungary has been attacked by students who were supported by academic heads of research universities. In late October, 2011, students led by the National Student Association, HOOK, held protest demonstrations against planned changes in higher education at Budapest. With them were members of the European Students Union (ESU) and heads of several research universities (6.). Earlier, over 1000 students protested against the new education policy of the government in Debrecen University, in Eastern Hungary .The students were protesting against planned cuts in state funding of higher education and

curtailment of students rights. The demonstrations in Debrecen followed the protests in Pécs in the south and Sopron in the north-west (7)

Gaps in our knowledge

This brief survey of literature reveals that student power in Hungary is a social fact. Many countries have witnessed radical trends among students and youth in different periods of their history. This review of literature indicates that data is available on Hungarian student politics. But it also points to gaps in our knowledge. We need to know whether the concept of student radicalism can be applied in the twenty-first century Hungary. As far as we know from the extant publications available in English, no empirical study on student radicalism in the twenty-first century has been done on Hungarian students, though some news reports are available. Our focus will be on the attitudes of the Hungarian student-youth.

The setting

The present research was carried out in the Institute of Sociology and Social Policy, Corvinus University. Corvinus University is a leading university in Hungary. In 2000, the university was formed with the merger of several institutions of higher education. It was named Corvinus University in 2004. According to Tamás Mészáros, Rector of Corvinus University the university is "A humanist institution that brings together several disciplines from social sciences to the natural sciences"(24). In 2011, Corvinus University secured 15 out of 20 top positions of the state financed BA programs with the highest entry scores (24). The Institute of Sociology & Social Policy is one of the institutes of Corvinus University. According to its website, the institute offers one of the most popular sociology programmes, based on market demand, sociological theories, methodology and economics. It offers a BA in Sociology and MA in Local Development. (25) In addition, the institute has a collaborative **Joint European Masters in Comparative Local Development** programme with foreign universities, namely, University of Trento, Italy, University Belgrade, Serbia, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, University of Regensburg, Germany, Tshwane Institute of Technology, South Africa, and University of North Carolina, at Chapel Hill, USA, under the **Erasmus Mundus** Programme

Conceptual & Methodological Foundations

The Concept of Radicalism

The term radical is widely used in political and philosophical literature, though not always in an identical sense. In its sociological application, as Selden C. Meneff has pointed out, "the term applies in general to those who believe in drastic measures for the improvement of social conditions, and in particular to those who believe in and / or advocate sweeping changes in the political and/or economic structure of society." (12: 24) I have used the term radicalism in this sense. Egon Bittner speaks of two varieties of radicalism-left-wing and right-wing (29)

.I have used the concept of radicalism in the sense of left-wing radicalism only. Left –wing radicalism is an attitude that advocates radical change in society along a socialist direction. Right- wing radicalism, on the other hand, may incorporate ideologies like religious fundamentalism, linguism, ethnicity, etc.

Methodology

Methodology incorporates 1) the logic or philosophy of research and 2) the techniques of research. Following Marx, we may divide our methodology into two parts: the method of inquiry and the method of presentation. The method of inquiry, according to Marx, involves appropriating the material in detail, analysing its different forms of development, and tracing its inner connections. My method of inquiry is the survey method. I have done a pilot study on student radicalism in Hungary on the basis of a questionnaire which I field tested on the students of The University of Burdwan in India. The questionnaire contained some factual and attitudinal questions. On 14th November, 2011, I, helped by Faculty Members of the Institute of Sociology and Social Policy, Corvinus University, visited two MA classes. All the students who were present in these classes filled up the questionnaires. Prof.Zoltán Szántó,Prof.Agnes Czakó, and Prof.Helmido Dezó helped me in collecting data.

The *method of presentation*, on the other hand involves presenting the findings in such a way that the meaning and import of the findings become crystal clear. Only after the scientific method of inquiry has been properly followed, the subject matter of the inquiry can be adequately and effectively described. As Marx puts it, “If done successfully, if the life of the subject is reflected as in a mirror, then it may appear as if we had before us a mere a priori construction”(11:19)..My *method of presentation* will consist of simple statistical analysis and qualitative analysis.

Major Findings

Socio-economic background

There were 32 respondents. Among them 7(21.88%) were males and 25 (78.13%) were females. 8(25%) respondents came from rural areas and 24(75%) from urban areas. Ages wise, the overwhelming majority of the respondents were in the age group 22-24.2(6.25%) were aged between 18-21.28(87.5%) were aged between 22-24 years.2 (6.25%) were aged above 30years.

The students were asked about their family income. We find that 21(65.63%) belonged to lower income group. Their family income was below 160001 HUF.8 (25%) were from middle income group. Their family income ranged from 160001-400000HUF.3 (9.38%) came from higher income group. Their family income ranged from 400001-760000 HUF.

When asked about their parents occupations, the responses of the students varied. With respect to their fathers' occupation, 10 respondents (31.25%) did not answer the question. One (3.13%) was a factory worker, One (3.13%) was a office worker, 2(6.25%) were businessmen, 2(6.25%) were teachers (who include university professors). Four (12.5%) were professionals. 4 (12.5%) were mechanics 5(15.63%) were pensioners. In addition, there were three (9.38%) fathers who pursued other occupations which were not classified.

With respect to their mothers' occupation, 7 respondents (21.88%) did not answer the question. 1 respondent (3.13%) reported that his mother was unemployed, one (3.13%) was a factory worker and one(3.13%) was an office worker. 2 reported(6.25%) that their mothers were administrators, five (15.63%) were teachers(who include university professors), 10 (31.25%) were professionals, 2(6.25%) were pensioners, and three (9.38%) pursued other occupations like cooking which were not classified.

Opinions on Economic Problems of Hungary

Like many European countries, Hungary suffered from economic crisis in 2008-09 when the Depression badly hit the nation. According to The Economist, Hungary now has the lowest employment rates in the European Union (55%). One in three Hungarians lives below the poverty line. About 70% of all household and business debt is dominated by foreign currencies, like the Swiss franc (13). The collapse of the Hungarian forint and its uncertain future increased the woes of the people. The forint is likely to be replaced by the euro in 2012. The 25 billion dollar loan package from IMF and World Bank aimed to restore investor confidence which had been badly undermined. (14) It has been claimed that the loan led to economic recovery. (14) But London Thomas of The New York Times Magazine observed: "As for Hungary, the 25 billion dollar agreement it signed with the monetary fund last year (2008) has put it in an awful policy vise. Mandated to squeeze its budget deficit below 3 per cent of its gross domestic product, the government is in no position to stimulate an economy estimated to sink as much by six percent this year (2009)". (15)

How do Hungarian students view their economy?

With regard to economic problems of Hungary, the students offered a variety of answers. One student wrote that "In Hungary, nowadays there are big amounts of poor people, and the difference between them and the richer people is bigger and bigger." She also complained about high taxes, corruption, unemployment and inflation. A second respondent also pointed out that Hungarian economy is being dominated by multinational firms like Tesco instead of small shops owned by Hungarians. A third respondent alleged that Hungarian agriculture is being ruined.

Opinions on social problems of Hungary

Like many European societies, Hungarian society is in a state of transition. And this period of rapid social change results in anomie. Social scientists have studied social problems in Hungary. For example, István Vingender (16) studied the problem of drug addiction. Paul Hollander (17) studied the contribution of social sciences to the study of social problems in Hungary. Lively debates in cyberspace have also taken place, like the journalists' debate on the Roma gypsies. (18).

I asked my respondents to identify the major social problems in Hungary. Some of the major problems identified by them include the following: Romas and other ethnic groups, unemployment, poverty, inequality among classes, and crisis of values.

Opinions on political problems of Hungary

Students were also asked about the major political problems Hungary was facing. Most students were very vocal about the political problems their nation was facing. According to one respondent, "The biggest problem is that there are no strong party, which has exact plans for solving the major problems." A second respondent agreed. She argued that there is "too wide gap between the two political parties (right-left wings)".she added that "economic development is slow, unemployment is high, gypsy problem." A third respondent argued that the biggest political problem is "Our government right now". "Political parties have lost credibility, according to a fourth respondent." A fifth respondent has alleged that "The government curtails basic democratic rights" A sixth respondent says that "There is no single political force that I would vote for." Corruption is one of the top political problems identified by the many respondents. A seventh respondent argues "Corruption, lying, there isn't enough responsibility for making decisions, arguing all the time, there isn't a good cooperation between politicians. Everybody thinks of himself". Many respondents have also alleged that there are incompetent people in high positions. From this discussion it appears that students of Corvinus University are disenchanted with the political system.

The students, however, have good reason to be disenchanted with the political system. The present Prime Minister of Hungary, Viktor Orban, has been portrayed as a power hungry person by The Economist (13).It is alleged in the media that all democratic institutions are being destroyed by the Fidesz.. But the main Opposition party is no good. Jobbik, is viewed as "thuggish". (13).

Voting in elections

Though most of the Hungarian students do not participate directly in political activity, yet they do vote in elections. From our data we found that out of 32 respondents, 25(78.13%) voted in the last General elections. By contrast 7(21.87%) did not vote. Thus more than three fourths of the respondents exercised their franchise. This is good for Hungarian democracy. Those who did not vote were asked why they did not vote, mostly gave technical reasons. But one respondent wrote, "I am really not interested in politics." Are some of Hungarian youth becoming alienated from the Hungarian political system?

Opinions on Achievements of Present Government

When asked about their opinions about the achievements of the present government, 16 out of 32 (50%) respondents did not answer the question. From an analysis of the answers given by the rest we also find that there is a palpable sense of disenchantment with the government. Some of the respondents wrote "I don't think they had any" or "There is no such thing". Another respondent wrote, "I don't follow their work. Sorry". But some respondents made positive appraisal of the government. One of them suggested that the government has a "Cohesive national policy, new constitution, basic reform in every policy, managed the Presidency of the EU, destroyed the unity of the left-wing." Others suggested that the government fights against public and personal debt, solves the credit problem.

Opinions on failures of present government

On the question of the major failures of the present government, the students offered a variety of answers. They may be grouped under political, economic and educational, cultural and health, failures. On the economic front, students pointed out that the government has imposed a high rate of taxes on the service sector, failed to check inflation, failed to solve the problem of poverty, centralized pension funds and is partial to business. On the educational, cultural and health issues, the respondents pointed out that the law on education does not reflect the needs of students. The government has also failed to fund cultural institutions. The respondents complained that the government is not dealing properly with public health. But the most severe criticism of the government is in the political front. The government stands accused of not communicating properly with the people, of taking key decisions too fast, and without discussion, of curtailing freedom of speech and expression, curtailing freedom of the media, curtailing the power of the constitutional courts, of introducing an unbalanced constitution. One respondent pointed out that the position of Hungary in European Union is bad. In fine, the government of the day stands accused by the educated youth of failing on all fronts. One student wrote: "I am not proud being a Hungarian."

Attitude to radical social change

Hungary was one of the countries of Eastern Europe where socialism was introduced after the Second World War. In the late eighties, however, socialism collapsed and was replaced by liberalism. Since then, Hungary has had a capitalist society. I was interested in knowing whether the youth of Hungary were interested in radical social change along socialist lines. I had asked the respondents questions on radical social change based on Marxist theory. These include-“Should private property be abolished? Would you support a society in which there are friendly classes? Do you think that socialist society is the best form of society? Should the capitalist state be replaced by the socialist state?” I would regard those who agree on all these questions as radicals, those who disagree on all these questions as conservatives, and those who agree on some items but not on others are inconsistent radicals or liberals.

Of the 32 respondents, 17(53.13%) claimed to be not acquainted with Marxism. This is a surprising finding, considering the fact that the study of Marx’s thought is part of the compulsory papers a student has to study in the BA course in Sociology. It is quite natural that these students had no attitude to radical social change. Of the 15 students (46.87%) who were acquainted with Marxism, 6 (40%) were conservatives and 9(60%) were liberals. There were no radicals among the students surveyed.

But the students surveyed had strong opinions with regard to capitalism and socialism. One respondent opined that capitalism was good but socialism was human centred, because it did not rate people by their actions in the market. A second respondent claimed that capitalism gives opportunity for mobility and freedom. A third respondent opined that liberal democracy is the best type of government but there should be a social network to help people in need. A fourth respondent wrote that socialist state structure showed its discrepancies in the last century. Socialism is good in theory but it does not work in reality.

Which Government Works Best?

Thus the majority of the students are liberal in their attitude. This overall attitude to social change is reflected in their political preferences as well. . On being asked “Which government works best?”-25 respondents, i.e., 78.13% preferred liberal-democratic government. 1(3.13%) preferred absolute monarchy, and 6(18.75%) claimed that no government works best.

Opinions on Student Participation in Politics

We know that students in Hungary have lately played a very militant role in opposing what they consider to be regressive policies of the Hungarian state. In October 2011, they have protested against planned budgetary cuts in higher education and the heads of research universities have supported their movement (6.). Now let us examine the issue of student political participation from the perspective of the student community.

Unlike Indian universities, Calcutta University, Burdwan University or Jawaharlal Nehru University, we find no evidence of student political activism in Corvinus University. No political posters, banners, etc., are found in the campus. With respect to political participation inside the campus; we find that no student participates in campus politics. Outside the campus, however, we find that some students do participate in political activity. Three students (9.38%) reported that they participate in political activity outside the campus. Thus the overwhelming majority of the 32 students studied (90.62%) do not participate in politics.

In answer to the question, "Should students participate in politics"? –21 respondents (65.63%) advocated student participation in politics. 11 students (34.38%) opposed student participation in politics. Thus the majority of the respondents favoured student participation in politics.

On further probing, those who support student participation in politics gave a variety of opinions in support of their answers. One respondent said that since students are future leaders of the country, they must be provided every opportunity for participating in politics. A second respondent' said that students should participate in politics in order to protect their interests. A third respondent remarked that politics and higher education may go together. A fourth respondent wrote that participation does not only mean volunteering for a political party. It also means giving opinions, voting, demonstrating or supporting, for example, on the Internet.

Those who oppose student participation in politics also voiced their opinions. One respondent remarked that students should learn about politics in the universities. Similarly, a second respondent remarked students are not ready to participate in politics. They should first learn about politics and later participate in it.

Concluding Observations

I have been doing research on student radicalism for the last twenty-five years. By radical social change, I mean fundamental changes in society along socialist lines. Till now, I had studied student radicalism in India (27, and 28). In India, the prospect of radical social change may generate theoretical interest, but in practice left parties are not as powerful as to capture state power through elections or other means. But this is the first time that I am doing research on student radicalism in a country that had experienced socialism since the end of the Second World War till the late eighties of the twentieth century. I thought that it would be interesting to know whether the present generation of university students would be in favour of radical social change at a time when capitalism is in deep crisis throughout the world. Capitalism has been under attack in countries of advanced capitalism, like USA and

UK. In the European Union too, capitalism is in crisis. Recently, In Greece, Italy and Spain, governments have fallen because they have been unable to tackle the economic crisis, and create employment opportunities. France is also reported to face a widening debt crisis. Interestingly, the governments which fell were led by socialist parties. People are now rebelling against capitalism. The Occupy Wall Street Movement (20, 21) and

similar movements like Occupy London have shown (22) that people are no longer willing to tolerate the ills of capitalism. They feel betrayed. They are accusing greedy corporations and corrupt governments of ruining them. Is a socialist revolution the solution?

Hungary was a socialist state, but why was it replaced by neo-liberalism? According to János Kis, "Society never considered the Communist system to be legitimate, but tolerated it as long as it succeeded economically. When the economic successes ran out, so did public tolerance and the Communist leadership class soon found itself to be badly undercut." (23:4). Our data shows that though the educated Hungarian youth are highly critical of their social, economic and political system, none of them are radicals in the sense that they want a socialist revolution. One respondent writes that "Socialist state structure showed its discrepancies in the last century. Socialism is good in theory but it does not work in reality". His views on socialism reflect the views of many of the students. But there is a minority opinion which regards socialism is more humane than capitalism. We may hypothesise that liberalism is the dominant ideology of the educated youth in Hungary. It is significant that more than three fourths of the respondents favoured liberal-democratic government as the best form of government. Is this tilt towards liberalism the result of continuous official anti-Communist propaganda? The Hungarian Ministry of Foreign affairs, for example, is showcasing the 1956 Movement which it termed the "The Hungarian Revolution" in foreign countries.(30) Before I came to Budapest , I saw an exhibition on "The Hungarian Revolution" in the Hungarian Cultural Centre, New Delhi.

The present study is a pilot survey, done in one of the major institutes of Corvinus University, namely, the Institute of Sociology & Social Policy. Due to limited time and money, the author could undertake just a small pilot study. While recent news reports on the political orientations of Hungarian students (2) and researches reported in the Press (5) show that Hungarian students are moving to the right, our micro-study on Corvinus University students contradicts these commonsense notions and research findings. We find that Corvinus University students favour liberal democracy. But, at the same time, they are highly critical of their government.

Let me now suggest some policy measures .Firstly, the government should reverse the policy of cost cutting in the field of education. We find that any country that has taken a loan from the IMF has been forced to cut expenditure and go for austerity measures. And this cost cutting usually takes a toll of social services, like education and health-two critical areas where the government should be actively involved. This is a problem which is faced by not only Hungary, but by India as well. But, from my reading of the political situation in Hungary, I think that if the Hungarian government reduces support to the education system, it risks alienating not only educated youth but also the intellectuals who teach in the universities.

Secondly, a more intensive education of children and youth on Hungarian society and polity should be undertaken right from school to the universities. To prevent racism, fascism and neo-Nazism from dominating youthful minds, the Hungarian state supported education system should give emphasis on social and political education of the youth. A course in the social sciences should be made compulsory for all students. Unfortunately, too much emphasis is being given to technology and its relation to business and too little to the

social sciences in the European Union. At the IT Net Conference (16-18 November, 2011) in Corvinus University, Prof. Karl Marmarosch presented a paper entitled "From laboratory to the tropics: Failure and success". Prof. Leen Hordjik dwelt on career opportunities in the Joint Research Centre of the European Union which laid emphasis on science and technology (26:25-26). Similarly, Mr. Tomohiro Tamiguchi's address dwelt on nuclear safety. Prof. Adnan

Badran lectured on technology centric research throughout the world and its relation to business. All the above mentioned topics no doubt have relevance to contemporary Europe and the world. But none of the speakers spoke on the relevance of social sciences in solving the social problems of the contemporary world. Yet it is the social sciences alone which can guide the State in formulating policies designed to solve social problems.

Before I conclude, I would suggest leads for further research. Data from the present study can form the basis of a larger research project encompassing the entire Corvinus University. Future researchers may make a comparative study of student social and political attitudes, covering two universities within Hungary, like Corvinus University, and the University of Debrecen. Cross-cultural comparisons, like comparing Corvinus University in Hungary, with say, The University of Burdwan in India, will also be fruitful. They will uncover new dimensions of student radicalism. In fine, this research has added a little to the sociology of youth in general and to the study of student radicalism in particular. Therein lies its significance.

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